

THE IMPORTANCE OF STUDYING PHYSICS AND THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICS IN THE MODERN WORLD

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Abstract .We offer physics courses that meet a variety of goals students may have in studying physics, take elective courses to improve scientific literacy, meet requirements for a science or engineering major, or pursue a degree in physics or engineering physics. get a degree. Physics courses reveal the mathematical beauty of the universe on a subatomic to cosmological scale. physics usually focuses on the general nature of the natural world through mathematical analysis. Society's dependence on technology represents the importance of physics in everyday life.

Keywords: MRI, radiotherapy, medicine, Magnetism, electricity, conductors, television, computers, telephones, home technology, aircraft and telecommunications, matter, energy, Electromagnetic radiation, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scanners, X-rays, cancer treatments for radiation therapy, ventilators for patients whose lungs cannot breathe.

Introduction

Electricity- One of the greatest discoveries that mankind has made is electricity, by understanding the physics properly we have been able to turn it into something useful for electricity, which is just a giant pile of electronics. By creating a voltage difference in something as simple as a battery, we can move the electrons that are the basis of electricity, the moving electrons that make the circuits that allow the operation of radios, televisions, lights and electronics, any other electronic device. Travel and transport - Due to the main role of transport in the modern era, one of the most successful fields of application of the statistical physics of complex networks is the study of traffic dynamics, but most of the works consider transport networks as isolated systems, which is contradictory. many complex networks with nontrivial interdependence. To simulate a real scenario, we use a multilayer network system to create a two-layer traffic model, where the upper layer provides a higher traffic rate than the lower layer. Medicine-Physics has made very important contributions to health since the advent of medicine 5,000 years ago, and these contributions are many and varied, including diagnostic X-rays, nuclear medicine, clinical PET scanning, magnetic resonance imaging, magnetoencephalography has been and remains so. , MRI, radiotherapy treatment, minimally invasive surgery, interventional magnetic resonance imaging, photonics, scaling theory, and high-intensity focused ultrasound with a combination of diagnosis and treatment. These contributions will increase as the molecular mechanisms of disease are better understood and new technologies allow the in vivo investigation of these molecular processes, with medical physicists, for example, playing an important role in ensuring patient safety, safe and effective implementation. new health technologies based on physics. Technology-Physics has helped us expand medical technology, for example we have examples from physics: magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scanners, X-rays, radiation therapy for cancer treatments, and ventilators for patients with lung failure. For example, GPS satellites. To account for the relativistic effects of the motion of their companions, they agree on their internal time, Einstein's special theory of relativity describes the period dilation experienced by rapidly vibrating objects. The importance of physics in everyday life. Physics is heavily involved in the application of physics in everyday life and in a number of activities we do and things we

use in our daily lives. Physics is a natural science because it deals with things like matter, force, energy and motion. Since all of these are related to tasks related to everyday life, we can say that physics explains how the universe works, how the Earth moves around the sun, how lightning ignites, how our refrigerator works, and many other things. will try Physics - When we study and discuss physics, we focus a lot on energy, which is a fundamental element of science, to better understand this connection, it is useful to refer to a strong working definition of physics. Physics is an important mechanism for educating chemists, engineers and computer scientists, and for professionals in various physical and biomedical sciences, in the same way that it enhances and refines our knowledge of other methods, such as earth, agricultural sciences. , chemical, biological, and ecological, as well as astrophysics and cosmology, important categories of evidence for all parts of the world. Physics helps to improve the quality of life by providing the basic concepts needed to develop new methods and techniques for use in medicine, such as: CT scan, Magnetic resonance imaging, Positron emission tomography, Ultrasound imaging, Laser surgery.Importance of Studying Physics-Physics is second only to mathematics in the purity of its principles, physics describes how the natural world works through practical mathematical formulas, it deals with the fundamental forces of the universe and they range from galaxies and planets to atoms and depending on how it interacts with matter. quarks and everything in between. All other natural sciences derive from physics, chemistry is mainly applied physics and biology is applied chemistry, the theory of physics is responsible for advances in electronics that lead to advances in modern computers and electronic media. Everything around us uses energy in one way or another, our cars, planes and trains burn fuel, our computers require power supplies and Wi-Fi connections, and our telecommunications devices are powered by cellular signals. more needs have arisen and this may be alternative energy sources such as nuclear energy or fossil fuels or hybrid energy.Why Studying Physics is Important-The purpose of physics is to understand how things work from first principles, we offer physics courses that match the different goals students may have in studying physics, we take elective courses to improve scientific literacy, meet requirements for a science or engineering major or have a degree in physics or engineering physics. Physics courses reveal the mathematical beauty of the universe from the subatomic to the cosmological scale, and the study of physics reinforces quantitative thinking and problem-solving skills that are valuable in fields beyond physics. Students studying the fields of Physics or Engineering Physics are able to consider developments in science and technology, academia, government or the private sector. Careers can focus on basic research in astrophysics, cosmology, particle physics, atomic physics, photonics or charged matter physics, or more rigorous research in areas such as renewable energy, quantum information science, materials engineering, biophysics or medical physics. Majors may also include management in teaching, medicine, law (especially intellectual property or patent law), scientific writing, history of science, philosophy of science, science policy, energy policy, government, or technical fields. Physics and engineering majors are excellent preparation for almost any career because they teach students to analyze complex problems and give them a strong quantitative foundation that can be applied in any technical field.Importance of Physics in Modern World-Physics covers all aspects of our life, it includes the study of matter, energy and their interactions, as it is a branch of science that includes all other sciences and other sciences depend on concepts and methods developed through physics. Other disciplines such as chemistry, agriculture, environmental and biological sciences use the laws of physics to better understand the nature of their research,

physics usually focuses on the general nature of the natural world through mathematical analysis. Society's dependence on technology represents the importance of physics in everyday life. . Many aspects of modern society would not be possible without the important scientific discoveries made in the past, and these discoveries were the foundation upon which today's technologies were developed. Discoveries such as magnetism, electricity, conductors, and more have created modern conveniences such as television, computers, telephones, and other business and home technologies, as well as modern vehicles such as airplanes and telecommunications. all based on physics concepts.

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Technology-Physics has helped us expand medical technology, for example we have examples from physics: magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scanners, X-rays, radiation therapy for cancer treatments, and ventilators for patients with lung failure. For example, GPS satellites. To account for the relativistic effects of the motion of their companions, they agree on their internal time, Einstein's special theory of relativity describes the period dilation experienced by rapidly vibrating objects. The importance of physics in everyday life. Physics is heavily involved in the application of physics in everyday life and in a number of activities we do and things we use in our daily lives. Physics is a natural science because it deals with things like matter, force, energy and motion. Since all of these are related to tasks related to everyday life, we can say that physics explains how the universe works, how the Earth moves around the sun, how lightning ignites, how our refrigerator works, and many other things. rganadi. When we walk, we actually move like an inverted pendulum, when we put our foot, it becomes our axis, and our mass is located in the abdominal cavity, describing the shape of an arc.

Fresh Egg-One way to know if an egg is rotten or good to eat is using the float test, to test whether the egg is good or not, the egg is placed in a glass of water, the fresh egg remains at the bottom. .glass, an egg that sinks but stays in the middle of the glass may be a little bigger but still cooked and eaten, because if the egg floats it's bad, all this is achieved thanks

to the importance of Physics. Climate-Climate is related to the absorption of solar radiation and the subsequent redistribution of this energy through radiative, advective, and hydrological processes. Soap is lighter than water, so when you make a bubble, the water is attracted to the bottom of the bubble and pushes the soap up, due to gravity, the surface tension of the water is greater than that of the soap. the top of the bubble shrinks as more soap accumulates at the top, and soon the internal pressure is sufficient to break the bubble and cause it to burst.

Used as Wifi-Radio waves Electromagnetic radiation, these waves transmit data by vibrating at different frequencies, these waves are very important for Wi-Fi to work well, electromagnetic waves are the same as mechanical waves have characteristic components, such as wavelength, amplitude, frequency, but do they behave very differently.

How physicists think about physics-Philosophy of physics begins with the findings of particular theories in physics and then deals with the consequences and puzzles that arise, such as the nature of determinism or the relative or fixed nature of space or time. people are better suited as philosophers. Einstein was first and foremost a philosopher, and his colleagues deserve some credit for that, and relativity was a metaphysician until he provided ways to incorporate it into physics.

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